

stand than in pure stands at all fertility levels except at zero added fertilizer. Higher fertility levels significantly increased plant height of both cultivars. The prismatic shape of the mixed stand canopy allowed more light to reach the plants and resulted in greater LTR than in pure stands of both cultivars at all growth stages (see figure). LTR was least in Mahsuri pure stand. LTR decreased gradually as fertility levels increased and decreased more in pure than in mixed stands. □

LTR in rice cultivars grown in pure and mixed stands at different fertility levels.

Dormancy of IR50 seeds

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IR50 seeds obtained at harvest were evaluated for dormancy. Immediately after harvest, they had 14.7% moisture and 15% germination. But when stained with a 0.25% solution of tetra-zolium chloride, the seeds showed 92% germinability, which indicated the presence of dormancy.

The seeds were sun-dried for 3 d from 0930 to 1130 h and from 1400 to 1700 h, shade-dried, or dried at 40°C in a hot-air dryer. Moisture content and percentage germination were recorded 1, 7, 14, and 27 d after harvest (see table).

At 14 and 27 d after harvest, shade-dried seeds were soaked in water for 24 h and tested for germination (see table). □

Moisture content and gemination of IR50 seeds at different days after harvest, Coimbatore, India.

Days after harvest	Drying treatment	Moisture content (%)	Germination (%)
Fresh	—	15	15
	Sun	12	22
	Shade	13	20
	At 40°C	13	26
7	Sun	9	85
	Shade	10	25
	At 40°C	9	70
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	78
14	Sun	10	87
	Shade	10	44
	At 40°C	10	86
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	83
27	Sun	9	85
	Shade	10	82
	At 40°C	10	83
	Soaking and leaching of shade-dried seed	—	83
CD (0.05)		3	4

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Comparative biology, pathology, and karyology of rice and maize isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii*

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We compared six Indian isolates of maize and rice sheath blight (ShB) pathogen

R. solani f. sp. *sasakii*, collected from Karnal (R₁), Solan (R₂), Sundernagar (R₃), Bajaura (R₄), Hyderabad (R₅), and Coimbatore (R₆). We evaluated range of nuclei, mean and mode of nuclear number per hyphal cell, in vitro response to temperature, fungicide and antibiotic response, and relationship of temperature levels to disease intensity.

We found that rice and maize ShB pathogens were identical based on

positive cross-inoculation of the pathogen isolates; symptom similarity on *Saccharum officinarum*, *Paspalum scrobiculatum*, *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Zea maxicana*, *Zea mays* (varieties *indurata*, *indentata*, *saccharata*, and *everta*), *Setaria italica*, *Panicum miliaceum*, *Sorghum vulgare*, *Echinochloa frumentacea*, and *Pennisetum americanum*; similar sclerotial and mycelial characters; nuclear mode number (see table); similar range of

nuclei per hyphal cell; similar response of in vitro growth to temperature (see table); and disease development on maize inbred Cuba 257.

Responses of rice (R₆) and maize isolates (R₁) to carbendazim, benodanil, and thiabendazole were also similar. Two isolates, however, responded differently to thiophanate-M, dichloroline, and aureofungin. The rice isolate was more sensitive to dichloroline and less to thiophanate-M than the maize isolate, which failed to grow at the lowest thiophanate-M concentration (35 µg ai/ml). □

Comparison of maize and rice isolates of *R. solani* f. sp. *sasakii*, New Delhi, India.

Isolate	Origin	Nuclei/hyphal cell		Mode nuclear no.	Growth rate (mm/24 h)		Disease developed ^a on maize inbred Cuba 257 at			Mean virulence on 7 hosts ^c
		Range	Mean		25°C	30°C	25°C	30°C	35°C ^b	
R ₁	Maize	4-8	6.6	6	47	45	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.6
R ₂	Maize	3-13	6.6	6	37	37	1.5	1.5	+	2.0
R ₃	Maize	3-11	6.3	6	46	47	2.0	2.0	+ ^d	2.6
R ₄	Maize	3-13	6.3	6	27	35	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.9
R ₅	Rice	3-16	7.0	6	46	44	1.0	2.0	+	2.5
R ₆	Rice	3-9	5.4	6	47	47	3.0	3.0	+	2.7

^aDisease recorded on maize inbred Cuba 257 on 1-5 scale. ^b+ = growth in traces. ^cAverage of 4 readings each on 7 hosts. ^d production of infection cushions.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Rice varietal reaction to leafroller (LF) and yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We evaluated 6 promising 120- to 140-d rices for reaction to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in an adaptive research trial at Thozhudur, Thanjavur District, in 1983 thaladi when there was severe insect pressure.

Ten plants from nonreplicated plots of each variety were randomly chosen for scoring. LF reaction was based on the number of affected leaves in relation to the total leaves. YSB was scored based on the number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant. Scoring was at flowering in Nov.

LF incidence ranged from 2 to 12%. Co 44, Pusa 169, AD9408, and Co 43 had resistant reaction. All varieties but Co 44 had fewer than 20% deadhearts, indicating YSB resistance (see table). □

Rice varietal reaction to LF and YSB incidence, Thozhudur, India.

Variety	Infestation (%)	
	LF ^a	YSB ^b
IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya)	11	11
AD9408 (IR20/IR8)	3	15
BS8 (IR36/Co 13)	12	8
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	8	18
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	2	23
Pusa 169 (IR28/P140)	2	19

^aBased on number of affected leaves in relation to total leaves. ^bBased on number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant.

Rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in the Solomon Islands

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About two and one-half annual irrigated rice crops are grown under mechanized cultivation on the Guadalcanal Plains of the Solomon Islands. The local BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål population is highly virulent and resistant varieties only last 1-3 yr. We continually screen varieties for BPH resistance.

BG379-5 (BG96-3/Ptb 33) is believed to possess the Ptb 33 resistance gene and was first screened for BPH resistance in the 1980 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery. It was highly resistant,

Yield and resistance of BG379-5 to pests^a on the Guadalcanal Plains, Solomon Islands.

Seeded	Harvested	Resistance ^b to			Yield (t/ha)	Remarks
		BPH	LR	ShB		
29 Jul 83	28 Nov 83	1.5	1.0	4.0	7.3	Heavy ShB incidence
11 Aug	12 Dec	1.0	1.0	—	4.6	Stunted and yellowing
20 Oct	16 Feb 84	2.0	1.0	2	3.8	Moderate army worm damage
29 Oct	5 Mar	1.4	1.0	3	5.3	—
26 Nov	28 Mar	1.4	1.0	—	6.2	Moderate brown spot incidence
17 Dec	18 Apr	3.0	1.5	5.3	4.8	Heavy army worm attack
20 Jan 84	18 May	4.5	1.0	2	5.0	—
10 Feb	7 Jun	7.3	1.0	—	4.0	60% hopperburned
19 Mar	16 Jul	7.0	1.0	—	4.9	—
6 Apr	21 Jul	6.0	1.0	—	3.4	—

^a LR = leafroller, ShB = sheath blight. ^bRated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*: 1 = most resistant, 9 = most susceptible.

scoring 1 on the 1-9 IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* and yielded 7-8 t/ha. It was released for commercial use on the Solomon Islands in 1982 and until recently has shown BPH resistance.

To monitor BG379-5 performance, we conducted yield trials from Jul 1973 to Jul 1984. Seeds were planted monthly in randomly chosen 3- × 5-m plots with 4 replications. Thirty, 40, and 40 kg N/ha